

ASSESSMENT ON THE EXTENT OF THE ADHERENCE TO DEPARTMENT OF TOURISM IMPLEMENTED HEALTH GUIDELINES OF SELECTED BEACH RESORTS IN NONONG CASTO, LEMERY, BATANGAS

Ma. Kristal Mhaye M. Amido, Shaina Rose M. Balmes and Mike Angelo B. Tarcelo,
Dr. April M. Perez

*College of Accountancy, Business, Economics and International Hospitality Management,
Batangas State University*

Email Address: april.perez@g.batstate-u.edu.ph

ABSTRACT

The purpose of this study is to assess the extent of the adherence to Department of Tourism implemented health guidelines of selected beach resorts in Nonong Casto, Lemery, Batangas. The study determined the assessment of the extent of the adherence to department of tourism implemented health guidelines of selected beach resorts in Nonong Casto, Lemery, Batangas in terms of Guest Handling Policy, Reception and Concierge, Rooms and Housekeeping, Food and Beverage (F&B) Services, and Public Areas. The researchers used the descriptive design method of research to gather necessary data needed in the study. This method was used to supply proper course of action to the selected beach resorts. Furthermore, the respondents of the study were guests of the beach resorts which has a total number of 380. Moreover, to obtain answers, the researchers used survey questionnaire as the main data gathering tool. The findings of the study revealed that majority of respondents are in the age of 22-41 years old, male, single, high school graduate and spending under Php 3,499. Also, there is a significant difference among the assessment on the respondents in terms of age, sex, civil status, educational attainment and monthly income. Furthermore, extension program were proposed to areas of concern in selected sections to further enhance the level of adherence of beach resorts to the implemented health guidelines of department of tourism.

Keywords: adherence, public areas, health guideline, guest handling policy, beach resorts.

1. INTRODUCTION

The COVID-19 pandemic is having a major impact on the country's tourist and hospitality sectors. Many countries and their governments chose to temporarily close schools, gyms, shops, churches, restaurants, hotels, and even resorts to flatten the curve and prevent social gatherings during the Coronavirus (COVID-19) pandemic, which began in 2020. We all know that the Philippines is among the most affected countries in Asia, and our government has chosen to put the country on lockdown in order to avoid a full-fledged pandemic. The government issued rules in a number of areas in May 2020 to ensure that the beach resorts will adhere to the guidelines for the safety of the guests and the employees.

Furthermore, beach tourism makes for a major portion of the overall national revenue in many nations that offer "sun, sea, and sand" (3S) tourist. As a result, governments are under pressure to restore beaches as soon as there is a decline in COVID-19 cases, if not sooner, under stringent monitoring and control methods. According to Botero and Zielinski [1], guests must be treated with the utmost respect and care, which is why managers must create a healthy culture environment. On the other hand, the employees or workers from these establishments should not overlook the internal and external environment of an establishment is equally important because without them, any accommodation institutions or

firms will cease to exist. The safety and security of guests and employees are under the jurisdiction of managers in accommodation establishments. That's why managers should continually plan and update their health protocols. This should be appropriately anchored from a factual source and compatible to an accommodation establishment. They must also apply appropriate precautionary measures for the management of health of all the people inside. Health experts developed these Health Safety Guidelines because they regard life. Being safe and secure during a pandemic is a benefit that people must not take for granted. It is also important to remember that simply implementing these policies is not enough; guests, workers, and management must all observe and comply with them. In light of the recently imposed health guidelines, the research explores the extent to which the above-mentioned rule is implemented in order to completely comprehend the current situation of selected beach resorts in Nonong Casto, Lemery, Batangas. To be successful, team effort must be exerted to attain a safe place for everyone.

In line with this, According to Adel [2], beach resort in the Philippines, was reported to closure for allowing a staged beach party that violated the government's COVID-19 regulations. The beach resort gained news after some resort guests were seen on film partying by the coast without wearing facial protection or face shields, as recommended by

health officials. The partygoers were also shown on film not keeping their distance from one another.

2. OBJECTIVES

The objectives of the study was to determine the profiles of the respondents in terms of age, sex, civil status, educational attainment and monthly income and to assess the extent of the adherence to department of tourism implemented health guidelines of selected beach resorts in Nonong Casto, Lemery, Batangas.

3. MATERIALS AND METHODS

The researchers used survey questionnaire as their main data gathering instrument. In addition, the descriptive method of research was used to gather necessary data needed in the study. This type of research design was appropriate one to use to collect and describe the present condition of the subject of the study and to attain the exact result and findings. This method was used to supply proper course of action to the selected beach resorts. The respondents of the study were the guests of beach resorts. The researchers believe that the guests hold the answers to their questions. Moreover, the guests are the ones who experience the services and have the ability to observe if the new implemented guidelines were adhered with great extent in different beach resorts in Nonong Casto, Lemery, Batangas. The total number of respondents were 380. The data gathered was then classified and tallied. To arrive at a clear interpretation, the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) was employed in the statistical analysis of data. The following statistical tools were used in the study:

Frequency and Percentage. It was used to determine the profile of respondents in terms of age, sex, civil status, educational attainment and monthly income. This was used to dividing the numbers of responses by the number of participants.

Weighted Mean. This was used to assess the extent of adherence to the department of tourism implemented health guidelines of selected beach resorts in Nonong Casto, Lemery, Batangas.

Independent T-Test. This was used to determine the significant difference on the assessment of the extent of adherence to department of tourism implemented health guidelines of selected beach resorts in Nonong Casto, Lemery, Batangas when the respondents was grouped according to sex.

One-way Analysis of Variance (ANOVA). ANOVA was used to determine the significant difference among the profile of respondents and their assessment of the extent of adherence to department of tourism implemented health guidelines of selected beach resorts in Nonong Casto, Lemery, Batangas.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1. Profile of the Respondents

The profile of the respondents in terms of age, sex, civil status, educational attainment and monthly income were analyzed and interpreted.

4.1.1 Age

Table 1 presents how respondents were distributed according to their age. The respondents' profile in terms of age was given consideration in the study.

Table 1
Distribution of the Respondents in Terms of Age

Age	Frequency	Percentage
21 years old and below	81	21.3
22-41 years old	251	66.1
42-59 years old	44	11.6
60 years old and above	4	1.1
Total	380	100

It shows that out of 380 respondents, most respondents belong to the 22 – 41 years old age bracket with a frequency of 251 and a percentage of 66.1. It is then followed by the 21 years old and below old age bracket having a frequency of 88 and a percentage of 21.3. Followed by 42-59 years old age bracket with a frequency of 44 and a percentage of 11.6. Ranking fourth is the 60 years old and above age bracket with a frequency of 4 and a percentage of 1.1.

Based on the result of the survey, researchers have led to believe that 22-59 years old age brackets dominated the survey because they are allowed to go out and travel for the reason that they are permitted by the Inter-Agency Task Force in accordance with the New Further Amended Health Protocols in Accommodation Establishments. They also belong to the age bracket who have enough income to spend on leisure and travel. Due to the pandemic, travelers book their vacation with families so that they could avoid crowded places and maintain their safety. On the other hand, they could clearly see that the senior citizens ranked last. This age bracket is prohibited by the Department of Health because most of them have weaker immune system than other age bracket.

According to Inter-Agency Task Force [3], stated that Individual outdoor exercises may be allowed to people who are not otherwise required to stay in their homes. The exercise of individuals under the age of 18 and over 65, as well as people with immunodeficiencies, comorbidities, or other health risks and pregnant women, shall be permitted but limited to within the general area of their residence, such as the barangay, purok, subdivision and/or village.

On the other hand, in the study of Falvo et al., [4], older adults or people aged 65 or older have been disproportionately affected by the COVID-19 outburst in several ways, leading some scholars to define it as a “geriatric health emergency.” They also stated that older age is associated with more severe courses of COVID-19 hospitalization, the

need for a ventilator to support breathing, intensive care, and mortality. This is one of the reasons why the older age must not be seen in public areas. That's also why most of them stay in the comfort of their homes. The safety of older people should be the number one priority.

4.1.2 Sex

Table 2 shows how the respondents were distributed according to their sex. The respondents' profile in terms of sex was given consideration in the study.

Table 2
Distribution of the Respondents in Terms of Sex

Sex	Frequency	Percentage
Male	230	60.5
Female	150	39.5
Total	380	100

As seen in Table 3, majority of the respondents were male with a frequency of 230 and a percentage of 60.5. On the contrary, the female respondents have a frequency of 150 and a percentage of 39.5.

The numbers presented in the table shows that there are more male than female respondents in terms of sex. The researchers believes that there were both male and female in beach resorts. However, it was dominated by men. Men were more likely to travel on the other hand, women were more likely to follow the rules.

According to Kiefer [5], men are more than twice as likely to take risks. In 2020, less than half of male travellers, whereas half of them don't wear masks or wash their hands, said they like to take risks when they travel. Conversely, only 21% of female travellers agreed with that statement. Furthermore, women are doing the family thing because more than half of women took a family trip in 2020 compared to 46% of men, and 38% took a road trip, compared to 27% of men.

4.1.3 Civil Status

Table 3 presents how respondents were distributed according to civil status. The respondents' profile in terms of civil status was given consideration in the study.

Table 3
Distribution of the Respondents in Terms of Civil Status

Civil Status	Frequency	Percentage
Single	276	72.6
Married	98	25.8
Widowed	6	1.6
Total	380	100

The table shows that most of the respondents belong to single category with a frequency of 276 and a percentage of 72.6. It is then followed by the married category having a frequency of 98 and a percentage of 25.8. Ranking on its third is the widowed category with a frequency of 6 and a percentage of 1.6.

In terms of civil status, a single category dominated because they are known to be less committed. Most singles don't have many

responsibilities, but they do have money and time, which are two of the most important resources that a guest must have when traveling or visiting beach resorts. Furthermore, single people are known for having an explorative personality and a desire to travel in multiple ways. According to Quinn [6], who wrote blog posts about single travelers, she said that one of the main reasons why there are more single travelers is because they only have to think about themselves which also means that you can change your mind as much as you want and make new plans all the time.

On the other hand, there are also guests from the married category, and the researchers noticed that there is a rise when it comes to family travellers during the pandemic. As heads of their houses, they ensured that all the family members were together and safe. A researcher describes how married people feel in times of COVID-19 "married individuals are more content with life if they spend longer time with their spouses, and less satisfied the more they spend alone.

4.1.4 Educational Attainment

Table 4 shows how respondents were distributed according to their educational attainment. The respondents' profile in terms of educational attainment was given consideration in the study.

Table 4
Distribution of the Respondents in Terms of Educational Attainment

Educational Attainment	Frequency	Percentage
High School Graduate	175	46.1
Vocational Course/ Non Degree	32	8.4
College Graduate/ Bachelor's Degree Program	163	42.9
Master's/ Doctoral Program	10	2.6
Total	380	100

The table shows that high school graduates rank first with a frequency of 175 and a percentage of 46.1 while college graduates rank in second with a frequency of 163 and a percentage of 42.9. Ranking on its third and fourth is the vocational course with a frequency of 32 and a percentage of 8.4 and master's degree with a frequency of 10 and a percentage of 2.6 respectively.

The number presented in the table between high school graduate and college graduate does not have a substantial gap in educational attainment considering that their difference is only twelve. The researchers assessed that these two tend to be more social and explorer type by looking for a place to relax. They are the group of people who spend their weekends with their friends and families by going

out and take a break from their online classes and work from home. Some high school graduates have their part time jobs and for college graduates they are usually employed and are earning salary. The higher the education level attained, the higher knowledge and awareness when it comes to new implemented health guidelines at accommodation establishments during COVID-19 Pandemic.

In another study of research decisions, it was discovered that education could lead to more accurate health beliefs and knowledge, and thus to better lifestyle choices, and better skills and greater self-advocacy. Furthermore, education improves skills such as literacy, develops effective habits and may improve cognitive ability.

4.1.5 Monthly Income

Table 5 shows how respondents were distributed according to their monthly income. The respondents' profile in terms of monthly income was given consideration in the study.

Table 5
Distribution of the Respondents in Terms of Monthly Income

Monthly Income	Frequency	Percentage
Under Php 3,499	117	30.8
Php 3,500-Php 4,999	51	13.4
Php 5,000-Php 8,499	58	15.3
Php 8,500-Php 20,999	77	20.3
Php 21,000-Php 41,999	58	15.3
Php 42,000 above	19	5.0
Total	380	100

The monthly income that ranks first is under Php 3,499 with a frequency of 117 and a percentage of 30.8. It is then followed by Php 8,500 – 20,999 monthly income with a frequency of 77 and a percentage of 20.3. Third in rank are the Php 5,000 – Php 8,499 and 21,000 – Php 41,999 monthly incomes with the same frequency of 58 and a percentage of 15.3. The fourth is Php 3,500- Php 4,999 monthly income with a frequency of 51 and a percentage of 13.4. Ranking last is Php 42,000 above monthly income with a frequency of 19 and a percentage of 5.0.

The data gathered from the respondents exhibited that the price of service of different beach resorts was not necessarily a substantial factor for the respondents despite their low income. The researchers have led to believe that respondents were more inclined to have fun and relax at different beach resorts due to long lockdowns rather than worrying about the money being spent. They are easily satisfied as long as the beach resort service is affordable or at a reasonable price. On the other hand, individuals with higher income are pickier with their choice of beach resort as they expect a safer environment during this pandemic, they

expect and seek more with the value of money they are spending on.

According to Ahmed et al., [7], income level helps the consumer in making decisions about spending, whether the consumer should spend a certain amount over luxuries or opt to save that amount. People at higher income levels tend to spend more on their consumption and need for luxuries with improvement in income. Moreover, a study by Karki & Panthi [8], believe that occupation of customers has an impact on guest satisfaction because those who are earning less or are in low level job, are satisfied easily such as students, clerks etc. however, those who are at higher level management position are pickier about services that has been given to them.

4.2 Assessment on the Level of Extent on the Adherence of the Selected Beach Resorts in Nonong Casto, Lemery, Batangas

The extent of the level of adherence to the department of tourism implemented health guidelines of selected beach resorts in terms of Section 5. Guest Handling Policy, Section 6. Reception and Concierge, Section 7. Rooms and Housekeeping, Section 8. Food and Beverage (F&B) Services, and Section 9. Public Areas were assessed and analyzed in this study.

4.2.1 Section 5. Guest Handling Policy

Table 6 shows assessment on the level of extent on the adherence to the department of tourism implemented health guidelines to selected beach resorts in Nonong Casto in terms of Section 5. Guest Handling Policy.

Table 6
Assessment on the Level of Extent on the Adherence of Selected Beach Resorts in Nonong Casto in Terms of Guest Handling Policy

As a guest, does the beach resort adheres to the following guidelines?	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation
1. No facemask and no face shield, no entry policy.	1.67	Least Extent
2. Guests must be screened prior to entry in the Accommodation Establishment through: a. Body temperature check using a Thermal Scanner or Thermometer Gun; b. Completion of Health Declaration and Contact Tracing Form using a mobile application or other contactless means.	1.64	Least Extent
3. Cashless/online modes of payment using payment applications or online transactions shall be utilized by the Accommodation Establishment for reservations or bookings.	1.61	Least Extent
4. Guests shall be advised to disinfect their shoes using sanitizing mats and drying pads provided at the entrances.	1.53	Least Extent
5. Physical Distancing measures, hand hygiene, respiratory etiquette, and contactless greeting must be observed when handling guests at the check-in counter.	1.56	Least Extent
6. Staggered check-in and check-out times for billeted guests shall be scheduled to avoid crowding in front desks.	1.60	Least Extent
7. Online check-in / check-out system or other similar technologies are encouraged to be utilized to minimize waiting time at front desks.	1.58	Least Extent
8. Guests must be provided with appropriate information on the prevailing disease, as well as the policies enforced by the establishment to reduce the risk and spread of the disease.	1.61	Least Extent
9. Guests must be informed of the management policies on room occupancy, dining, and use of public areas imposed to ensure safety and reduce risk of infection.	1.62	Least Extent
10. No showing of guests around the room after check in.	1.54	Least Extent
11. Guests must be provided with reminder cards, which may include the following: 1. No sharing of food or any personal or non- personal belongings; 2. Proper disposal of used PPE; 3. Mingling with occupants of other rooms other than own family or group is prohibited; 4. Practice of proper handwashing etiquette/hand hygiene, respiratory etiquette, and proper use of face mask; and 5. Strict observance of Physical Distancing.	1.52	Least Extent
12. To minimize close contact, promotional flyers or items shall not be handed to customers in person. These items may be collected from tables or other designated areas.	1.57	Least Extent
Composite Mean	1.59	Least Extent

As shown on Table 6, the assessment on the level of adherence of beach resorts in Nonong Castro in terms of Guest Handling Policy acquired a composite mean of 1.59 and a verbal interpretation of least extent. Moreover, the researchers also assessed that one of the reasons why beach resorts were not adhering to a very great extent to the implemented health guidelines is due to lack of employees. Beach resort owners cannot hold many employees because of the new restrictions and fluctuating COVID-19 cases in Nonong Casto, Lemery, Batangas.

4.2.2 Section 6. Reception and Concierge

Table 7 shows the assessment on the level of extent on the adherence to the department of tourism implemented health guidelines to selected beach resorts in Nonong Casto in terms of Section 6. Reception and Concierge.

Table 7
Assessment on the Level of Extent on the Adherence of Selected Beach Resorts in Nonong Casto in Terms of Reception and Concierge

As a guest, does the beach resort adheres to the following guidelines?	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation
1. Official up-to-date information must be available at the reception desk about travel to and from countries and/or other areas, including local Destinations that are identified by the Department of Health (DOH) as high-risk in spreading the virus or disease.	1.57	Least Extent
2. Emergency contact numbers of public health authorities, nearest hospital or medical center, and the DOH Assistance Center must be readily available in the reception desk.	1.59	Least Extent
3. The following medical kit and PPE shall be readily available at the reception counter or desk.a. Germicidal disinfectant or wipes for surface cleaning;b. Face mask or face shield;c. Biohazard disposable waste bag;d. 70% solution alcohol or alcohol-based hand sanitizer;e. Tissue paper, napkin, or paper towel; and f. Disposable gloves	1.63	Least Extent
4. Floor markers that allow one (1) meter distance between guests on queuing must be in place to ensure physical distancing. Express lanes for PWDs, senior citizens, pregnant women, and parents with small children shall be provided.	1.57	Least Extent
5. Acrylic glass barriers or transparent dividers may be set up at the front desk for additional protection.	1.61	Least Extent
6. Front desk personnel attending to guests must wear face masks. Disposable gloves must be used when handling cash or documents, and/or materials that are passed from person to person. Contactless process at the front desk is mandatory.	1.61	Least Extent
7. All staff extending guest assistance that requires physical contact (e.g. wheelchair, bell service) must wear proper PPE, such as face mask and gloves, whenever necessary.	1.62	Least Extent
8. Hand-shaking is not advised, the practice of Filipino Brand of Service (FBS) or the "Mabuhay Gesture" in greeting and receiving guests, as well as other forms of contactless greeting, is highly encouraged.	1.58	Least Extent
Composite Mean	1.60	Least Extent

As shown on Table 7, the majority of the respondents have observed that the level of adherence of selected beach resorts to Section Reception & Concierge was at least extent which acquired a composite mean of 1.60. The researchers have led to believe that the Beach Resorts in Nonong Casto were not taking precautions in terms of reception and concierge, considering that the department is the first and last contact between guests and staff of the beach resorts.

This result has led them to believe that there is a lack of proper training and dissemination

of information about the safety and security of guests and also when it comes to the management of employees. This is still because of the scarcity of the workforce.

4.2.3 Section 7. Rooms and Housekeeping

Table 8 shows the assessment on the level of extent on the adherence to the department of tourism implemented health guidelines to selected beach resorts in Nonong Casto in terms of Section 7. Rooms and Housekeeping.

Table 8
Assessment on the Level of Extent on the Adherence of Selected Beach Resorts in Nonong Casto in Terms of Rooms and Housekeeping

As a guest, does the beach resort adheres to the following guidelines?	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation												
<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Room Floor Area (sqm)</th> <th>Maximum Number of Guests</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>Up to 20 sqm</td> <td>1 person or 2 persons from the same household</td> </tr> <tr> <td>21 to 29 sqm</td> <td>2 persons</td> </tr> <tr> <td>30 to 39 sqm</td> <td>3 persons</td> </tr> <tr> <td>40 to 49 sqm</td> <td>4 persons</td> </tr> <tr> <td>50 sqm and above</td> <td>5 persons</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Room Floor Area (sqm)	Maximum Number of Guests	Up to 20 sqm	1 person or 2 persons from the same household	21 to 29 sqm	2 persons	30 to 39 sqm	3 persons	40 to 49 sqm	4 persons	50 sqm and above	5 persons	1.58	Least Extent
Room Floor Area (sqm)	Maximum Number of Guests													
Up to 20 sqm	1 person or 2 persons from the same household													
21 to 29 sqm	2 persons													
30 to 39 sqm	3 persons													
40 to 49 sqm	4 persons													
50 sqm and above	5 persons													
1. Room Occupancy Policy- The maximum allowable guests staying in the guestroom at a given time shall be determined by the floor area of the guestroom, as follows:														
2. Only couples or family members who share the same household may be allowed to share rooms. A distance of 1 to 2 meters between the beds is highly encouraged.	1.50	Least Extent												
3. Co-mingling with other groups other than one's own family or group shall be strictly prohibited. The Rooms Division Department shall employ control measures to prohibit guests from mingling with other guests and / or from loitering to other rooms.	1.61	Least Extent												
4. Room transfers may be allowed when necessary.	1.57	Least Extent												
5. Trash bins must be provided inside the guest room. A separate trash bag or bin intended for used PPE such as face mask, gloves and other sanitation waste materials must be provided.	1.67	Least Extent												
6. Rooms must be set up to allow convenient in-room dining for guests.	1.52	Least Extent												
7. Guests shall be allowed to avail of room service provided that the food and beverage be delivered by the doorstep of the guestroom. Guests shall leave used dining crockery, utensils, and wastes outside their room for retrieval of housekeeping staff.	1.57	Least Extent												
8. Reusable napkins and placemats shall be prohibited. Cutlery and tableware shall be available upon request and shall be dispensed with directly to guests when dining inside the room.	1.56	Least Extent												
9. Laundry bags shall be given to guests should they want to avail of laundry services. Guests shall leave their bagged dirty clothes at the doorstep for housekeeping staff collection. Towel and linen replacements shall also be left at the doorsteps should the guests wish to change their linens.	1.66	Least Extent												
10. Guests shall be required to present proof of residency such as a government or company ID with a residential address.	1.62	Least Extent												
11. 70% solution alcohol or alcohol-based hand sanitizer/ disinfectant sprays, paper towels and or wipes shall be available inside the guest rooms and shall be replenished as necessary.	1.59	Least Extent												
12. A safety tag / label / signage indicating that the room has been thoroughly cleaned and sanitized prior to guest occupancy shall be affixed in the guestroom door.	1.58	Least Extent												
13. Room turndown service is highly discouraged. Cleaning and sanitation of rooms shall be conducted only as may be necessary.	1.61	Least Extent												
Composite Mean	1.59	Least Extent												

As shown on Table 9, the assessment on the level of adherence of beach resorts in Nonong Castro in terms of Rooms and Housekeeping acquired a composite mean of 1.59 and a verbal interpretation of least extent. The guidelines were not adhered to in terms of the rooms and housekeeping which could be a problem because the guests are staying in the beach resort in no less than 24 hours.

The respondents assessed that the beach resorts were not well equipped enough to operate since the composite mean falls at least extent level of adherence to the Department Of Tourism: Implemented Health Guidelines in Rooms and

Housekeeping. Moreover, it is essential that rooms are well ventilated and sanitized as the virus can travel from person to surface and vice versa. The numbers of pax in a room occupancy must also adhere because of physical distancing, which is a big help in decreasing the spread of the virus.

4.2.4 Section. 8 Food and Beverage Services

Table 9 shows assessment on the level of extent on the adherence to the department of tourism implemented health guidelines to selected beach resorts in Nonong Casto in terms of Section 8. Food and Beverage (F&B) Services.

Table 9
Assessment on the Level of Extent on the Adherence of Selected Beach Resorts in Nonong Casto in Terms of Food and Beverage Services

As a guest, does the beach resort adhere to the following guidelines?	Weighted mean	Verbal Interpretation
1. Personal Protective Equipment and Sanitation Material. The restaurant proprietor must provide employees with their respective PPEs, to be worn, when necessary while on duty, such as: a) Facemasks; b) Face shield; c) Alcohol (70% solution alcohol) / alcohol-based hand sanitizer; and d) Other equipment apparel that will ensure and promote the safety of the employees.	1.61	Least Extent
2. Cleanliness within the premises. The restaurant proprietor must ensure cleanliness within all its premises, including the lobbies, storage, back areas, and parking.	1.63	Least Extent
3. Notices. Notices or reminders on the restaurant health protocols shall be posted at the entrance and other conspicuous areas of the restaurant a) Completion of Contact Tracing Forms; b) "No mask, No Entry" policy; c) Physical Distancing protocols; d) Maximum number of allowable persons; 4 e) Cautious schedule and procedures; f) Alternative methods of payment; g) No customer-personnel contact protocols; h) Other protocols, including the right to refuse service to customers who fail or refuse to comply with protocols.	1.63	Least Extent
4. Mandatory Screening. Customers and Suppliers must be screened prior to entry in the Restaurant through: a. Body temperature check using a Thermal Scanner or Thermometer Gun; b. Completion of Health Declaration and Contact Tracing Form using a mobile application or other contactless means.	1.58	Least Extent
5. Physical Distancing. Customers shall observe physical distancing of at least one (1) meter from one another in communal areas, such as dining areas, toilets, and queue areas.	1.68	Least Extent
6. Sanitizing Mats. Sanitizing mats and drying pads shall be installed at the entrance of the restaurant, unless other entrances such as mall entrances, hotel entrances, etc. leading to the dine-in restaurants have already provided this.	1.55	Least Extent
7. Tables and Seating Arrangement. The restaurant seating capacity should allow at least one (1) meter spacing between customers. Chairs and tables shall be distanced at least one meter on all sides.	1.60	Least Extent
8. Tables shall be arranged such that the distance from the back of one chair to the back of another chair shall be more than one (1) meter apart. If seats are fixed, alternate seats shall be marked out.	1.59	Least Extent
9. Face-to-face contact in tables shall only be permissible when transparent dividers (e.g. acrylic plastic, plexiglass, sneeze guards, etc.) are installed.	1.63	Least Extent
10. Menus. As far as practicable, a menu shall be displayed on the counter or other conspicuous area, or a single menu, QR code-based or any other touch less menu shall be placed on the customer's table.	1.60	Least Extent
11. Signage. Signage or notices must be installed in conspicuous areas reminding customers to wash their hands with soap and water for at least twenty (20) seconds or disinfect with 70% solution alcohol or alcohol-based hand sanitizer upon entering and leaving the restaurant.	1.61	Least Extent
12. Self-service and Condiment Stations. Self-service stations like do-it-yourself customer refill and condiment stations shall be prohibited until further notice.	1.60	Least Extent
13. Pick-up or take-away zones. As far as practicable, there shall be designated pick-up or take away zones for customers whose orders are for take-out.	1.58	Least Extent
14. Queuing System. Queue lines shall be provided with floor markers, demarcations, stanchions, signage, or tubers to ensure one (1) meter distance between customers on all sides.	1.53	Least Extent
15. Leisure Facilities. The operation of ancillary leisure facilities and amenities, such as in-lobby play areas, libraries, karaoke machines, etc., if any, shall be temporarily suspended.	1.59	Least Extent
16. Loud or Ambient Music. The use of loud or ambient music shall be kept to a minimum to discourage loud talking, which increases the likelihood of droplet transmission. (DTI MC 2020-39)	1.54	Least Extent
17. Hygiene, Grooming, and Other Conduct. Employees must observe personal hygiene, good grooming and other proper conduct while on duty, such as the following: a) Wearing of clean clothes or uniform, and closed shoes; b) Wearing of appropriate PPE while on duty; c) Refraining from wearing jewelry such as rings, bracelets, watches, and earrings; d) Practicing proper respiratory etiquette, such as covering of nose and mouth when coughing or sneezing; e) Avoiding physical contact with customers; f) Strictly observing of physical distancing in the working areas (e.g. kitchen, cashier, food storage areas, etc.); g) Washing of hands for 20 seconds before and after handling food, or at least once every hour or after close contact with customers; h) Not loitering in other areas outside of work stations and not engaging in close interactions not necessary for work; i) Not spitting on any surface in the restaurant.	1.63	Least Extent
18. Contact with Food Products. Employees shall avoid touching with their bare hands ready-to-eat food. Instead, they shall use appropriate utensils such as tongs, single use gloves, or dispensing equipment. If the task requires direct contact with ready-to-eat food, employees shall wash their hands and the exposed portions of the arms for 20 seconds prior to donning gloves and before touching food or food-contact surfaces. Hands shall be washed immediately after removing gloves.	1.57	Least Extent
19. Food Covering. Food shall be properly covered before it is served to the customer.	1.63	Least Extent
20. Contactless Transactions. Cashless or online modes of payment using payment applications shall be utilized by the Restaurants both for dine-in and delivery. If online or mobile payment is not possible, Restaurants shall create a method for no-contact payment schemes, such as receiving cash on a small tray or leather bill folder to avoid manual hand contact with customers.	1.56	Least Extent
21. Clean as You Go Policy. Employees must emulate the "Clean As You Go" policy by keeping the work area clean and tidy throughout the working day.	1.65	Least Extent
22. Ventilation and Exhaust. Proprietors of Dine-in establishments shall enhance their exhaust system, ensure better airflow inside air-conditioned restaurants, or install high-efficiency particulate air (HEPA) filtration systems. Outdoor dining (i.e. siting dining) is highly encouraged. (DTI MC No. 2020-39)	1.51	Least Extent
Composite Mean	1.59	Least Extent

Table 9 shows that the majority of the respondents have observed the level of adherence of selected beach resorts to Section 8. Food and Beverage (F&B) Services was at least extent which acquired a composite mean of 1.59. There have been many articles and researches about hygiene and garbage disposal issues at beach resorts in Lemery, and specifically in Nonong Casto even before the pandemic. Furthermore, there are few restaurants available nearby at selected beach resorts, and

common outlets which can be found at the vicinity were only carinderias.

Based on reliable sources, the researchers believe that this is due to premature reopening of beach resorts; they returned from the operation without proper preparation and plan. They are forced to open since people were longing for relaxation and escape due to the long lockdown brought by Enhanced Community Quarantine.

4.2.5 Section. 9 Public Areas

Table 10 shows assessment on the level of extent on the adherence to the department of tourism implemented health guidelines to selected beach resorts in Nonong Casto in terms of Section 9. Public Areas.

Table 10
Assessment on the Level of Extent on the Adherence of Selected Beach Resorts in Nonong Casto in Terms of Public Areas

As a guest, does the beach resort adhere to the following guidelines?	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation
Sanitizing mats and drying pads must be available at all entry points.	1.59	Least Extent
Cleaning and disinfection measures in common areas (e.g. lobby, restrooms, halls, corridors, elevators, etc.) must be applied as a general preventive measure. Special attention must be given to objects that are frequently touched such as elevator button, handles, handrails, switches, doorknobs, kitchen surfaces, etc.	1.63	Least Extent
Sanitation stations must be set up within the workplace and areas frequented by customers and guests.	1.66	Least Extent
Trash bins must be available and accessible in all areas of the establishment. These must be sanitized every after disposal or trash collection. Used facemasks, gloves, and other disposables shall be disposed immediately in a trash bin with cover or in tightly sealed bags.	1.58	Least Extent
Information, Education, and Communication (IEC) materials on proper handwashing, respiratory etiquette, and proper use of facemask and other safety and health-related information must be posted in conspicuous areas, particularly at the restrooms and other wash areas.	1.58	Least Extent
Health and Safety Protocol officer(s) shall be deployed in convergence areas to ensure the enforcement of Minimum Public Health Standards. Adequate supply of soaps, alcohol-based hand sanitizer, toilet paper and paper towels in the restrooms must be ensured.	1.58	Least Extent
Public toilets and restrooms must be cleaned and sanitized regularly every two (2) hours or as may be necessary.	1.62	Least Extent
Recreational areas or facilities such as gym and wellness centers, children's areas, sports facilities, swimming pool, etc. may be allowed to operate but with strict observance of DOH prescribed Minimum Public Health Standards and DTI Memorandum Circular 2020-44. In any case, special cleaning and disinfection protocols should be applied to these facilities.	1.56	Least Extent
Group activities shall be limited to no more than five (5) participants. For more than one group sharing a space, the groups shall not interact and shall maintain a distance of three (3) meters apart. For organized programs and classes, an additional service provider (such as an instructor or a coach) permitted/recognized by the establishment may guide the group.	1.57	Least Extent
Guests who intend to go swimming shall be advised not to wear facemasks when swimming. Allowed number of guests in a given time must be indicated to avoid crowding. Since face masks are not allowed in the swimming pool, physical distancing is a must.	1.59	Least Extent
Composite Mean	1.60	Least Extent

As shown on table 10, the majority of the respondents have observed the level of adherence of selected beach resorts to Section 9. Public Areas was at Least Extent which acquired a composite mean of 1.60. The researchers assessed that public areas were overcrowded, which increases exposure and hence transmission of COVID-19. Overcrowding occurs when the number of individuals exceeds the space available, resulting in adverse health outcomes, such as infectious diseases like COVID-19.

The researchers believe that overcrowding happened because of not adhering to the proper

floor markers and physical barriers. This technique is used to maintain proper social distancing and prevent guests' overcrowding where it is possible to separate employees and visitors where social distancing is not an option.

4.3 Significant Differences on the Assessment of the Respondent on the Extent of the Adherence to Department of Tourism Implemented Health Guidelines of Selected Beach Resort when Grouped According to Profile.

This presents the significance difference on the assessment of the respondents when grouped according to their profiles in terms of age, sex, civil status, educational attainment and monthly income.

4.3.1 Age

Table 11 presents the differences in the assessment of the respondents on the extent of the adherence to the department of tourism implemented health guidelines of selected beach resorts when grouped according to age.

Table 11
Differences on the Assessment of the Respondents on the Extent of the Adherence to Department of Tourism Implemented Health Guidelines of Selected Beach Resorts when Grouped According to Age

Variables	p-values	Computed f-values	Decision on Ho	Verbal Interpretation
Guest Handling Policy	.001	19.173	Reject Ho	Significant
Reception and Concierge	.001	18.382	Reject Ho	Significant
Rooms and Housekeeping	.001	20.294	Reject Ho	Significant
Food and Beverage Services	.001	19.368	Reject Ho	Significant
Public Areas	.001	18.546	Reject Ho	Significant

It is clearly shown in table 11 that there is a significant difference on Guest Handling Policy, Reception and Concierge, Rooms and Housekeeping, Food and Beverages and Public Areas in terms of extent of the adherence to the new implemented health guidelines of beach resorts in Nonong Casto, Lemery Batangas when grouped according to age as indicated by p-value of .001 which is less than .05 level of significance.

Age shows significant difference in terms of the extent of adherence to the new implemented health protocols of the Department of Tourism. Young adults are less cautious in their surroundings since they are young and they believe to have stronger immune systems making them more confident in traveling and staying outside their houses. On the other hand, older adults are more cautious knowing that they have weaker immune systems compared to younger adults. Since the start of the pandemic, people tend to believe that older

people have a higher possibility of being infected by the virus.

According to World Health Organization [9], most people infected with the virus will experience mild to moderate respiratory illness and recover without requiring special treatment. However, some will become seriously ill and require medical attention. Older people and those with underlying medical conditions like cardiovascular disease, diabetes, chronic respiratory disease, or cancer are more likely to develop serious illness. Anyone can get sick with COVID-19 and become seriously ill or die at any age.

4.3.2 Sex

Table 12 presents the differences in the assessment of the respondents on the extent of the adherence to the Department of Tourism implemented health guidelines of selected beach resorts when grouped according to sex.

Table 12
Differences on the Assessment of the Respondents on the Extent of the Adherence to Department of Tourism Implemented Health Guidelines of Selected Beach Resorts When Grouped According to Sex

Variables	p-values	Computed t-values	Decision on Ho	Verbal Interpretation
Guest Handling Policy	.06	-1.889	Failed to Reject	Not Significant
Reception and Concierge	.05	-1.970	Failed to Reject	Not Significant
Rooms and Housekeeping	.070	-1.815	Failed to Reject	Not Significant
Food and Beverage Services	.034	-2.129	Reject Ho	Significant
Public Areas	.018	-2.368	Reject Ho	Significant

It is clearly shown in table that there is a significant difference on Food and Beverages and Public Areas in terms of extent of the adherence to the new implemented health guidelines of beach resorts in Nonong Casto, Lemery Batangas when grouped according to sex as indicated by p-value of .034 and .018 respectively which is less than .05 level of significance. With regards to food and beverage services and public areas sex shows differences in their perceptions. With regards to foods, females are more likely to be observant in foods.

On the other hand, it is in table that there is no significant difference on Guest Handling Policy, Reception and Concierge, Rooms and Housekeeping in terms of extent of the adherence to the newly implemented health guidelines of Beach Resorts in Nonong Casto, Lemery Batangas when grouped according to sex as indicated by p-value of .06, .05, .070 respectively which is greater than .05 level of significance. With regard to Guest Handling Policy, Reception and Concierge and, Rooms and Housekeeping, there was no significant difference in the assessment of the respondents in terms of

their sex. Both sexes value the importance of being protected when it comes to socializing with the beach resorts' employees. These people greet and interact with employees from Guest handling, Reception and Concierge and even in the Rooms and Housekeeping department.

4.3.4 Civil Status

Table 13 presents the differences in the assessment of the respondents on the extent of the adherence to the department of tourism implemented health guidelines of selected beach resorts when grouped according to civil status.

Table 13
Differences on the Assessment of the Respondents on the Extent of the Adherence to Department of Tourism Implemented Health Guidelines of Selected Beach Resorts when Grouped According to Civil Status

Variables	p-values	Computed f-values	Decision on Ho	Verbal Interpretation
Guest Handling Policy	.001	6.967	Reject Ho	Significant
Reception and Concierge	.001	10.555	Reject Ho	Significant
Rooms and Housekeeping	.001	9.12	Reject Ho	Significant
Food and Beverage Services	.001	9.004	Reject Ho	Significant
Public Areas	.001	8.52	Reject Ho	Significant

It is clearly shown in table that there is a significant difference on Guest Handling Policy, Reception and Concierge, Rooms and Housekeeping, Food and Beverages and Public Areas to extent of adherence to the new implemented health guidelines of beach resorts in Nonong Casto, Lemery Batangas when grouped according to civil status as indicated by p-value of .0001 which is less than .05 level of significance.

The respondents have significant differences in terms on the extent of the adherence to the department of tourism's newly implemented health guidelines of selected beach resorts when grouped according to civil status because they have different priorities. Single individuals tend to just enjoy the leisure of traveling since they are alone, they only tend to care for themselves. While, when families travel together or married couples, they are more cautious since when one of them gets affected by the virus the other one has a higher risk of getting the virus since they are together. Also, traveling with family is more risky since as parents they must consider the health of everyone in their family knowing that all ages might get affected by the virus. According to Hamermesh [10], describes how married people feel in times of COVID-19 "married individuals are more content with life if they spend longer time with their spouses, and less satisfied the more they spend alone.

4.3.5 Educational Attainment

Table 14 presents the differences on the assessment of the respondents on the extent of the adherence to department of tourism implemented health guidelines of selected beach resorts when grouped according to educational attainment.

Table 14
Differences on the Assessment of the Respondents on the Extent of the Adherence to Department of Tourism Implemented Health Guidelines of Selected Beach Resorts When Grouped According to Educational Attainment

Variables	p-values	Computed f-values	Decision on Ho	Verbal Interpretation
Guest Handling Policy	.176	1.656	Failed to Reject	Not Significant
Reception and Concierge	.162	1.722	Failed to Reject	Not Significant
Rooms and Housekeeping	.042	2.761	Reject Ho	Significant
Food and Beverage Services	.050	2.630	Failed to Reject	Not Significant
Public Areas	.076	2.31	Failed to Reject	Not Significant

In terms of Rooms and Housekeeping there is a significant difference in terms of extent of the adherence to the new implemented health Guidelines of Beach Resorts in Nonong Casto, Lemery Batangas when grouped according to educational attainment as indicated by p-value of 0.42 which is less than .05 level of significance.

Educational Attainment reveals that there is a significant difference on how they view rooms and housekeeping. With higher levels of education, individuals are more likely to be particular with their choices. This may be the cause of unpleasant past experiences, this group of people do not want to experience poor quality of service. This makes them particular about the cleanliness and safety of the room and they want a comfortable environment during their stay. On the other hand, individuals with lower levels of education have low levels of awareness and expectations when it comes to choosing an accommodation. This group of people are not that exposed to different accommodation protocols which makes them easy to be pleased and satisfied.

It is shown in that there is no significant difference on Guest Handling Policy, Reception and Concierge, Food and Beverages and Public Areas with regards to extent of adherence to the new implemented health Guidelines of Beach Resorts in Nonong Casto, Lemery Batangas when grouped according to educational attainment as indicated by p-value of .176, .162, .050 and .076 which is greater than .05 level of significance. The respondents assessed Guest Handling Policy, Reception and Concierge, Food and Beverages, and Public Areas as the same and that it does not really affect their assessment regardless of their educational

background. When it comes to observing the environment of an accommodation establishment, all people from different levels of educational attainment feel the same way, this is because safety is their top priority.

4.3.6 Monthly Income

Table 15 presents the differences on the assessment of the respondents on the extent of the adherence to department of tourism implemented health guidelines of selected beach resorts when grouped according to monthly income.

Table 15
Differences on the Assessment of the Respondents on the Extent of the Adherence to Department of Tourism Implemented Health Guidelines of Selected Beach Resorts When Grouped According to Monthly Income

Variables	p-values	Computed f-values	Decision on Ho	Verbal Interpretation
Guest Handling Policy	.244	1.347	Failed to Reject	Not Significant
Reception and Concierge	.061	2.135	Failed to Reject	Not Significant
Rooms and housekeeping	.017	2.810	Reject Ho	Significant
Food and Beverage Services	.068	2.072	Failed to Reject	Not Significant
Public Areas	.006	3.338	Reject Ho	Significant

In terms of Rooms and Housekeeping and Public Areas, there is a significant difference in terms of extent of the adherence to the new implemented health Guidelines of Beach Resorts in Nonong Casto, Lemery Batangas when grouped according to age as indicated by p-value of .017 and .006 respectively which is less than .05 level of significance. Monthly Income shows significant difference in terms of Rooms and Housekeeping and Public Areas. Guests with high income tend to be more sophisticated in terms of booking a particular room. Since, our respondents are staying overnight at the beach resort they make sure that the room they have chosen is clean and sanitized and the guests should feel comfortable during their stay. This is also true when it comes to public areas, these zones include parking areas, hall, walkways, lobby, outlets and other big spaces where people meet. These places are likely to be crowded with people.

It is shown in the table that there is no significant difference on Guest Handling Policy, Reception and Concierge and Food and Beverages in terms of extent of the adherence to the new implemented health guidelines of beach resorts in Nonong Casto, Lemery Batangas when grouped according to monthly income as indicated by p-value of .244, 0.61, and .068 and respectively which is greater than .05 level of significance. Guests are more likely to focus on their health safety rather than the money they spent during their stay.

According to the World Economic Forum [11], the report indicates that health and safety

precautions are currently more important in consumers preferring to stay than price. That heavily influences the variety of destinations they are willing to travel to.

5. CONCLUSIONS

From the findings, the following conclusions were drawn:

1. Majority of respondents are in the age of 22-41 years old, male, single, high school graduate and spending under Php 3,499.
2. The level of adherence to the new implemented health guidelines to the department of tourism of the selected beach resorts in Nonong Casto, Lemery, Batangas as assessed by the respondents was at least extent level in terms of Section 5. Guest Handling Policy, Section 6. Reception and Concierge, Section 7. Rooms and Housekeeping, Section 8. Food and Beverage (F&B) Services and Section 9. Public Areas.
3. There is a significant difference among the assessment on the respondents in terms of age, sex, civil status, educational attainment and monthly income.
4. Extension program were given to areas of concern in sections under Guest Handling Policy; Reception and Concierge, Rooms and Housekeeping, Food and Beverage Services, Ventilation and Exhaust and Public Areas to further enhance the level of adherence of beach resorts to the new implemented health guidelines of department of tourism.

6. RECOMMENDATIONS

1. Upon the assessment, the researchers suggested the Inter-Agency Task Force to further amend the Memorandum Circular Order No. 2020-002-B entitled "Amending Further the health and Safety Guidelines Governing the Accommodation Establishments Under the New Normal" and include the regular checking on the extent of adherence of the Beach Resorts to ensure a very great extent to the adherence not only in Nonong Casto, Lemery Batangas but as well as the whole Philippines.
2. Based on the findings, the researchers recommend the Department of Tourism with the help of the Municipality of Health Lemery to conduct random regular monitoring in the beach to ensure that they are adhering with very great extent to the implementation of health protocols.
3. Based on the survey, the researchers found that there is least extent to the adherence of beach resorts in Nonong Casto, Lemery Batangas therefore, they suggested that all the beach resorts in Nonong Casto, Lemery Batangas to constantly adhere to health guidelines in order to assure the safety of their guests.

4. Lastly, future researchers are highly encouraged to use this research as a basis to gain more knowledge and research further pertaining to the extent of adherence to the implemented health guidelines.

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